

Towards Truly Scalable Sustainable Flexible Optical Networks

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Abstract We review four years of studies on various applications of coherent point-to-multipoint transceivers enabled by digital subcarrier multiplexing. We highlight the benefits of this approach to realize truly sustainable, scalable, and flexible optical networks. ©2025 The Author(s)

Introduction

Telecommunication systems must continuously evolve to address novel applications^[1]. Advanced technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Beyond 5G (B5G)/6G, distributed/edge computing, are key to this evolution, driving user-focused innovations^{[2],[3]}. In addition, increased accessibility to high-speed connectivity, facilitated by the proliferation of broadband technologies, results in substantial growth in IP traffic^[4]. In this context, limitations of direct detection in the physical layer will require complementary coherent technology to increase capacity^[5], particularly in the fast-growing segment of metro access. In this network segment, IP traffic exhibits Hub-and-Spoke (H&S) patterns, which naturally align with a Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) architecture. In contrast, metro networks have been predominantly built with Point-to-Point (P2P) solutions, which allows connections only between Transceivers (TRXs) with identical data rates. Despite it is effective, this approach can be inefficient as it requires aggregating numerous streams (of growing capacity) electronically in the access layer with switches and Reconfigurable Optical Add and Drop Multiplexers (ROADMs) before entering the metro network. Here, the total flow can now be connected to the high-speed counterpart TRXs, as illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

Advances in deployable technology are driven by the reduction of Capital and Operational Expenditure (CAPEX & OPEX), while the development of sustainable, scalable, and adaptable networks aids in achieving this goal. Network flexibility is often achieved through multiplexing (e.g., statistical, time, frequency). These techniques, combined with software-configurability and intelligent TRXs,

enable sharing of common resources whenever possible and adaptation to time-varying traffic. Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) could become the key enabler for achieving scalable and flexible P2MP optical networks, as depicted in Fig. 1(b).

Coherent DSCM was proposed for optical transport in^[6] and implemented to provide robust optical transmission on long-haul links^[7]. In^[8], DSCM was proposed to realize, for the first time, coherent P2MP TRXs and was further developed in^{[9],[10]}. Two significant advantages of this solution are: (i) the possibility of using a filterless multiplexing; (ii) the inherent support of coherent Bidirectional (BiDi) transmission and coexistence with legacy Passive Optical Networks (PONs). In (i), for example, in Upstream (US) direction, P2MP TRXs can receive Digital Subcarriers (DSCs) from various sources without electronic aggregation, only using passive components (MUX), as shown in Fig.1(b). In Downstream (DS), the hub TRX broadcast the traffic to all leaf TRXs, and all DSCs will be locked to its predefined frequency provided by the hub^[9]. The second advantage makes DSCM TRXs ideal for PON overlay, front-haul, and backhaul/aggregation^[11]. This flexibility suits the increasing H&S-like traffic patterns in metro access, while enabling various new applications that will be discussed in the second part of this article.

This article outlines our work from the initial concept to the real product. It consists of three parts: (i) coherent P2MP DSCM-based TRXs; (ii) sustainable, scalable, and flexible optical networks; and (iii) various applications of this technology.

Coherent P2MP TRXs enabled by DSCM

One of the key elements of a P2MP optical network is the pluggable TRX and its Digital Signal

Fig. 1: (a) P2P and (b) P2MP with DSCM architectures.

Fig. 2: Exemplary of daily traffic variation and provisioned capacity in metro-aggregation network^[14].

Processing (DSP) engine. There are two main differences between the DSP of a Single-carrier (SC) TRX and a DSCM one (Fig. 5(a-b) in^[9]): (i) need of digital multiplexing/demultiplexing; and (ii) averaged signal feedback across parallelized DSP blocks for precise phase/frequency tracking and leaf laser adjustment in P2MP scenarios^{[9],[12]}.

The considered DSCM TRX^{[9],[10],[12]} can currently transmit at data rates up to 400G with a granularity of 25G. This is achieved with a symbol rate of ~ 3.75 GBd ($\sim 15\%$ FEC OH), per DSC, using dual polarization 16-Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM). The symbol rate is the result of an optimization between the linewidth of the commercial laser and the desired symbol. In fact, low symbol rates would increase the Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR) penalty induced by phase noise^[12]. Also, thanks to roll-offs $< 5\%$, narrow, adaptable guard bands are feasible, ensuring a comparable spectral occupancy and data-rate between a SC and its equivalent DSCM TRX. Current commercial modules accommodate 4, 8, or 16 DSCs and various modulation formats^[13].

Scalable Sustainable Flexible Optical Networks

Given the continuous growth of traffic, the physical limits of fiber, and the related increase in energy demands of telecommunication networks, future optical systems must be more scalable, sustainable and flexible to minimize Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) and ensure intergenerational compatibility. Next-generation optical networks will require efficient and simplified architectures to enable seamless upgrades, e.g., using a filterless approach. Rather than optimizing each component in isolation, a holistic approach should be embraced to minimize: (i) CAPEX by decreasing component count, limiting electronic aggregation stages and optical/electrical/optical (O/E/O) conversions, substituting ROADMs with couplers/splitters, and enabling Hardware (HW) reuse via software-configurability; (ii) OPEX through remote management, simplified operations, fewer truck rolls, and lower energy use by transmitting only what is needed. Space and building costs can be reduced through long-reach PONs^[15] and router bypass^[16].

The TRX presented in the previous section underpins this approach via an independent control of the DSCM, supporting frequency and statistical multiplexing. Together with a Software Defined Network (SDN)-controller, it allows a dynamic, energy-aware configuration and a longer useful life of the equipment and fiber infrastructure.

Enabling Next-Generation Optical Networks

DSCM TRXs offer enhanced flexibility compared to SC TRXs due to their 25G DSC granularity. This flexibility is pivotal for creating sustainable and scalable optical networks. The key advantages of these TRXs include: (i) Dynamic traffic allocation and reduction of power consumption by removing electronic aggregation^{[14],[17],[18]}; (ii) Simplification of metro networks by optical aggregation of horseshoes^{[19],[20]}; (iii) High- to low-speed TRXs connection: 400G P2MP hubs can accommodate up to 16 TRXs at 25G and can vary the allocation over time; (iv) BiDi transmission over single fiber/laser/wavelength to enable high capacity and reflection tolerant front-haul for B5G/6G^[21]; (v) Utilization of existing PONs to enable high-capacity services; (vi) Optimal usage of the optical spectrum^[22]; (vii) Flatter IP-architecture thanks to filterless^[23] and cross-domain operation by router bypass^[16]. Due to spatial constraints, we will briefly address only the initial four opportunities.

Dynamic traffic allocation offers two primary advantages: capacity re-utilization^[17] and energy efficiency^[18]. In^[17], we introduced clustering traffic using DSCM to facilitate more efficient utilization of the spectrum. Fig. 3 in^[17] shows that the spectrum of the network could be better used during low traffic at night. Thanks to the flexibility provided by the DSCs, this is possible by reallocating spectrum for new services, similar to a fiber-as-a-service approach, and reduces network power consumption by modifying the operational parameters of coherent DSCM TRXs (e.g., turning off idle DSCs)^{[14],[18]}. Fig. 2 shows the static allocated capacity of 100G SC TRXs (green) and the dynamic one of 100G P2MP units (violet), with the dashed black line depicting the variations in daily traffic.

Fig. 3: Two-horseshoe network configurations: (a) no aggregation (a); (b) with optical aggregation. \boxtimes are couplers/splitters.

Fig. 4: Filterless aggregation optical network and relative power imbalance across the optical tree.

Flexible optical aggregation enabled by coherent DSCM TRXs can considerably simplify the design of complex horseshoe networks^[19]. Figs. 3 illustrate an example of a horseshoe network provided by Telecom Italia Mobile (TIM) that mimics existing urban network topologies. In this analysis, for simplicity, the leaf nodes (circles) are connected to a single hub (square). Thanks to P2MP TRX, we can aggregate more horseshoes at the hub, thus reducing the HW needed and improving scalability. In Fig. 3(a), we do not aggregate the two horseshoes, so we need one hub TRX per segment ($2 \times 400\text{G}$), while in Fig. 3(b) both horseshoes can be served by a single high-capacity TRX. The optical aggregation can be carried out as long as there are DSCs available and the minimum Optical Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (OSNR) is above the required threshold. In case the number of DSCs increases above the available, then a new high-speed TRX will be needed. It is important to stress that for P2P TRX, the number of TRXs at the hub is equivalent to the number of lead nodes and clearly no aggregation between horseshoes would be possible. Furthermore, a switch would be needed to aggregate the traffic of the leaf nodes. In general, the higher the level of aggregation enabled by P2MP, the lower the number of TRXs needed. However, as network size increases, aggregation levels decrease because of being constrained by the network's minimum OSNR.

High-capacity PON as depicted in Fig. 4 could include single horseshoe networks, where leaf nodes are added to a tree structure. This type of architecture can be realized with P2MP TRXs with simple passive components^[24], or with Optical Add and Drop Multiplexers (OADM)^{[25],[26]} (\boxtimes). The full scalability is enabled thanks to P2MP TRXs and their robustness to power imbalance, reported in^{[24],[26]} between 10 and 14 dB. The com-

bination with OADM enhances the flexibility and scalability^{[25],[26]}.

High-capacity mobile front-haul is shown in Fig. 5, where a P2P link for front-hauling applicable to 6G deployment is illustrated. Crucial factors for the upcoming mobile transport include: (i) high-speed TRXs; (ii) BiDi transmission over a *single fiber* to support latency-critical B5G/6G applications^[27]; and (iii) simplified HW to eliminate costly dual-laser setups^[28]. To avoid a dual-laser, a single-laser -wavelength transmission (visualized in Fig. 5(b, c)) could be considered. However, as shown in^{[29],[30]}, this configuration can suffer from high penalties due to distributed and discrete reflections, which become particularly detrimental when US and DS share the same wavelength^{[21],[30]}. Fig. 5(d, e) illustrate an alternative method using DSCM, maintaining a single-laser -wavelength by interleaving DSCs for both US and DS in the frequency domain^[8]. We have shown that this configuration reducing the penalty caused by reflection to almost zero^{[21],[30]}. An additional benefit of DSCM for mobile transport is the ability to provision US and DS capacities symmetrically or asymmetrically according to the conditions of traffic varying over time.

Conclusions and Future Steps

Designing flexible, scalable, and sustainable optical networks requires extensive system planning beyond the optimization of individual components. By integrating architectural decisions with intelligent, configurable HW & Software (SW), while maximizing HW utilization, we are able to meet current requirements and address future challenges. This article proposes a solution that uses coherent DSCM P2MP TRXs, highlighting how they simplify networks, reduce energy consumption, improve flexibility through dynamic channel allocation and seamless integration with existing systems.

Fig. 5: BiDi over single fiber single laser single wavelength and reflection mitigation using DSCM.

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